

Effect of reinforcements on deformation and energy absorption performance of 2D auxetic structure

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Abstract:

Additive technologies enable the production of complex structures with high control over their geometric parameters. In the field of kinetic energy absorption, it is advantageous to use a structured material, because it has better energy absorption capacity to weight ratio compared to a bulk material. For high-performance absorbers, it can be beneficial to use auxetic structures due to their unique internal geometry. They provide better energy redistribution or higher indentation resistance compared to conventional structures, however, they do not achieve such high values of absorbed energy. This paper focused on the systematic design of the internal layout of a 2D auxetic structure to increase the absorption performance and outperform conventional structures. The study investigated an implementation of the reinforcements in the structure with subsequent explanation of plastic hinge formation and energy dissipation. Auxetic lattice structures represented by reinforced re-entrant honeycomb were manufactured using Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) from stainless steel 316L and NiTi alloy. Specimens were then tested with experimental and FEM quasi-static compression test. By using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technology and FEM analysis, deformation maps were created, which helped to gain a deeper understanding of deformation patterns. Obtained data resulted in description, how reinforcements influence the locations of plastic hinges, stability of deformation and the deformation pattern of the structure. Finally, the results led to the design of auxetic structure that was able to absorb more than 70% of energy per unit mass compared to the reference geometry, while decreasing the eng. stress fluctuations about 36%.

Keywords: Auxetic structure, energy absorption, reinforcements, Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF), stainless steel 316L, NiTi alloy

1. Introduction

There are several factors that determine a suitability of a metamaterial for high energy absorption application. These factors are maximum force reaction, densification value, engineering stress-strain characteristic, and weight of the structure. Last three mentioned can be summarized by a parameter Specific Energy Absorption (SEA) [1, 2]. Cellular structures (structures consisting of elementary cells distributed in two or three dimensions) are considered better energy absorbers compare to a bulk material, because they can absorb the same amount of energy while reaching much lower reaction force peak [3, 4]. This means more efficient and safe energy dissipation [2, 5–7].

Auxetic structures are structures with negative Poisson's ratio. Negative Poisson's ratio is caused by typical inner geometry architecture, e.g. struts pointing inward the structure (re-entrant structures). Unlike conventional metamaterial, when tensile load is applied, auxetic structure expands in both directions; when compression is applied, it shrinks [8, 9]. Auxetic structures can

offer better damping [10, 11], synclastic deformation [12–14], or better indentation resistance [15–17]. However, the best energy absorbers ($SEA > 20$ J/g) are still structures with positive Poisson's ratio (conventional structures, non-auxetic) [2, 18, 19]. But in some applications, e.g. in aerospace or military, it can be valuable to combine the properties of auxetic structures with high-performance energy absorption [4, 5, 20].

1.1. Prerequisites of high-performance energy absorber

To achieve a maximum value of SEA and an efficient use of material of the structure, there are several prerequisites that should be fulfilled.

First, the dissipated energy should be irreversible [1, 3]. To achieve this, metamaterial should be made from ductile material, that can undergo high plastic deformation [3, 4]. Gibson & Ashby [4] described three main deformation mechanisms depending on the bulk material from which the metamaterial is made. According to this, high-performance structure from ductile material should deform by “rigid arms rotation around plastic hinges”, while the irreversible energy dissipation occurs in that plastic hinges. However, the deformation mechanism can be affected by inner geometry of the structure, causing some deviations in the deformation mechanism. Such additively manufactured bulk material can be Stainless steel 316L [21] or NiTi alloy [22, 23]. Stainless steel 316L is a ductile material with high elongation at break value (40 %) and easy manufacturability, which predetermines it to be good for energy absorption [21]. NiTi alloy is a material with high potential for high-end engineering applications, such as aerospace, automotive, automation and control or electronics industries [24], including energy absorption, vibration reduction and structural adaptation [25]. For energy absorption, the shape memory effect [25, 26] and ductility [22, 23] of the material can be beneficial for high-performance structures and reusable energy absorption. [4]

Second, an engineering stress-strain characteristic should be *plateau*, meaning that there are no peaks and valleys within the curve. Structures under compression have three main eng. stress-strain curve characteristics after elastic deformation: *softening* (high peak, then fast drop, then slow increase); *hardening* (stable increase of eng. stress) and *plateau* (stable constant eng. stress). These characteristics depend mainly on the inner geometry of the metamaterial. While the *softening* and *hardening* characteristics have a model representation of that inner geometry, there is none for the *plateau* characteristic [27]. However, it can be achieved using metamaterials with low relative density and large number of individual cells [4, 27].

Third requirement is a high densification value. This means that the moment of all cell edges touching itself, resulting in steep increases in eng. stress, come in as late as possible [1, 4, 27].

1.2. High-performance structures

Studies [1, 2, 28] compared large numbers of structures by their energy absorption capacity and density. When compared together, two main groups can be identified. One group consists of structures with high value of SEA (> 20 J/g), second group consists of structures with almost *plateau* characteristic of eng. stress-strain curve.

Metamaterials in the first group were metal foams from AlSi10Mg [29] and Ti6Al4V [18], auxetic BCC-6H from [2], simple cubic structure with gradient strut diameter [19], BCCz made from BCC cells with different strut diameters [30], or TPMS Double Gyroid [31]. Most of them, however, had strongly *hardening* eng. stress-strain characteristic, so the potential of the structure was used only half as much as compared to ideal *plateau* characteristic. On the other hand, structures in the second group were the entire opposite [28, 32, 33] – reaching only a fraction of the SEA value (< 3.5 J/g), while having good *plateau* characteristic. Common feature of these structures was the sinusoidal pattern of deformed arms and auxetic behavior. For this reason, re-entrant honeycomb (RHC) auxetic structure was used in this study. RHC is also a geometry with great potential for enhancing the absorption capacity using reinforcements [34]. By changing its horizontal arms, modification called Double re-entrant honeycomb (DRHC) can be observed. This modification mimics the sinusoidal geometry presented in structures with good *plateau* characteristic [28, 32, 33].

1.3. Enhancing energy absorption capacity

When only part of the prerequisites of high-performance energy absorber is fulfilled, there are several methods to improve its performance. Gradient relative density can eliminate high peak stresses, enhance *SEA*, but also cause strong *hardening* characteristic [19, 35, 36]. Arm thickness optimization is useful for effective material use and for stabilizing deformation pattern [37, 38]. Reinforcements (e.g. extra ribs) can cause higher stiffness and *SEA* of the structure [34, 39], stabilize deformation pattern [40] and increase number of plastic hinges [41], but can also lead to higher peak of eng. stress at the beginning of compression. However, it is possible to eliminate this peak using slightly pre-deformed shape of struts in the as-built state [36, 41].

Mentioned studies investigated several different structures and methods of increasing *SEA*, but the effect of reinforcements on the deformation process and the effective material utilization of the structure was not studied in detail; the studies only quantitatively described the consequence of their use. Thus, the main aim of this study is a description of enhancing the energy absorption capacity based on the analysis of deformation mechanisms in the presence of cell reinforcements.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Methodology

The scheme of the workflow is captured in **Figure 1** and can be divided into three main phases. First phase investigated the effect of reinforcements on deformation and energy absorption capacity both numerically and experimentally. Testing was done using single unit cell with implemented reinforcements. By analysing this phase, know-how about the deformation mechanism was concluded. Second phase used this new knowledge in single-parameter analysis to design new high-performance auxetic structures. In third phase, the new designs were validated both numerically and experimentally by quasi-static compression tests and compared with reference auxetic structure without reinforcements.

Figure 1. A scheme of the main workflow of study.

Re-entrant honeycomb (RHC, **Figure 2a**) and *Double re-entrant honeycomb* (DRHC, **Figure 2b**) were used in this paper. Only the DRHC type was considered for high-performance structure.

Figure 2. Two types of *re-entrant* auxetic structure: a) RHC; b) DRHC; and c) tested parameters

An RHC cell of nominal size 10×10 mm with horizontal arms was used. To describe the influence of the reinforcement's position (parameter V), the effect of the remaining parameters (deflection of arms R_A and reinforcements R_R , thickness of arms t_A and reinforcements t_R) had to be eliminated. For this reason, a reinforcement geometry was identical to that of the arms ($R_A = R_R = 1.34$ mm and $t_A = t_R = 1$ mm). Parameter V was ranged from 0 mm to 2.5 mm with 0.5 mm step. Geometry and corresponding parameters can be seen in **Figure 2c**. **Table 1** summarizes the investigated configurations of single unit cell.

Table 1. Overview of investigated RHC unit cells and its names ($R_A = 1.34$ mm; $t_A = t_R = 1.0$ mm)

Config.	No Reinf.	V00	V05	V10	V15	V20	V25
V (mm)	-	0.0	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
Model							

2.2. Materials used

Two types of materials were used: stainless steel 316L (EN 1.4404, TLS Technik GmbH, Germany) and NiTi alloy (CT-NiTi-EAAB, Carpenter Additive, United Kingdom). Mechanical properties are given in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of stainless steel 316L [21] and NiTi alloy [42]

Material	ρ_s (kg m^{-3})	E_s (GPa)	μ (-)	$R_{p0.2}$ (MPa)	R_m (MPa)	E_t (MPa)	A (%)
316L	7950	166	0.25	450	541	89	40.7
NiTi	6340	30.75	0.3	430	-	-	-

The samples were manufactured using SLM 280^{HL} machine (SLM Solutions Group AG, Lübeck, Germany) with the following set-up of process parameters given in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Process parameters for SLM manufacturing from [21] and [43]

Process parameter	316L	NiTi
Platform heating	100 °C	200 °C
Inert atmosphere	N ₂	Ar
Oxygen level	<0.2 %	<0.2 %
Layer thickness	50 μm	50 μm
Scanning contours	100 W, 300 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	360 W, 1250 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
Hatching	275 W, 700 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	360 W, 1250 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
Hatch distance	120 μm	115 μm
Fill contours	150 W, 400 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	-

2.3. FEM analysis

FEM analysis was performed in ANSYS Workbench 2025 R1 (Ansys, Inc., Canonsburg, USA). The simulations were done in the Static Structural module as a non-linear problem. A 2D *Plane Strain* geometry was used. Wall thickness in CAD model was adjusted to an average value from measuring the manufactured samples. A new bilinear material model for 316L was created using properties

listed in **Table 2** and calibrated with experimental testing, hence the tangent modulus was changed to $E_t = 890$ MPa. For NiTi alloy, a multilinear material model was defined with parameters mentioned in **Table 2** according to [42]. Upper and bottom plate was defined as rigid body. The mesh was generated from elements of type *Plane 183* (quadrilateral with 8 nodes), and their size was set so that the arms and reinforcements consisted of at least 5 elements.

Quasi-static compression tests were performed with boundary conditions assigned to upper and bottom plate (**Figure 3a**). Contacts between arms and reinforcements were set as *Frictionless*, while contacts between sample and plates were set as *Frictional* with coefficient of friction 0.2. Free movement in x-direction of the upper plate was used to capture the potential sensitivity of reinforced structure to small imperfections occurring in real conditions. Obtained force-displacement curve was transformed into eng. stress-strain curve.

Figure 3. a) BCs and mesh for FEM simulations; b) Real wall thickness measured on manufactured samples (detail)

2.4. Experimental validation

Each designed sample configuration was tested in 3 specimens. Outer dimensions were checked after manufacturing using callipers. Wall thickness was measured using Olympus SZX7 (Evident, Tokyo, Japan) at least at ten locations to determine the real value of t_A and t_R (**Figure 3b**).

The quasi-static compression test was performed with testing machine SHIMADZU AGX-100kNV2 (SHIMADZU CORPORATION, Japan). Compression speed was set to 1 mm/min up to compression of 5 mm.

The compression tests were recorded using two DIC cameras (5MPx CMOS camera, 2 Hz; Istra 4D V4.10 software, Dantec Dynamics a/s, Skovlunde, Denmark).

2.5. High-performance auxetic structure

The development of the structure was a systematic process in the form of single parameter analysis to achieve stable deformation and enhanced energy absorption performance. The knowledge gained from analysis of the single unit cell was used in forming the new geometry of the structure with optimal values of R_A , R_R and t_R . The simulation setup was similar to that described in **Section 2.2**.

To validly test the structures, it was necessary to determine the minimum number of cells. A sufficient number of cells meant that further increase did not change the *SEA* by more than 10%. Simulations were performed for DRHC structures (with implemented reinforcements) for initial number of cells 1×1, 3×3, 5×5, 7×7 and 9×9. Boundary conditions were as follows: right and bottom sides of the structure were prevented from moving in a direction perpendicular to these sides. The remaining outer edges of the structure were compressed by a value causing 10% strain of the whole structure (**Figure 4a**). This method eliminated the global buckling of the structure, so the *SEA* value was affected only by the number of cells.

Next step was single parameter optimisation. Boundary conditions for the simulations performed during this phase were considered as shown in **Figure 4b**. The range of investigated

parameters was: $R_A = R_R = 1, 1.5, 2$ and 3 mm; $V = 0, 1$ and 1.5 mm; $t_R = 0.5, 0.75, 1$ mm and *combined*. The *combined* thickness differentiated between horizontal ($t_R = 0.75$ mm) and vertical ($t_R = 0.5$ mm) reinforcements. The goal was to achieve a deformation of all reinforcements simultaneously, which was not observed for the uniform thickness in preliminary simulations.

Figure 4. a) BCs for determination of minimum number of cells; b) BCs for remaining simulation of this phase (x_0 and y_0 are initial dimensions of the structure)

Manufacturing and experimental testing of the structures were done in the same manner as with single unit cell (Section 2.4). Compression speed was set to 5 mm/min up to compression of 30 mm.

3. Results and Discussion

The following section describes the results from the experimental testing and FEM analysis, as well as a discussion of the results and their implications for the design of a high-performance structure for energy absorption.

3.1. FEM analysis and Experimental validation

A check of samples after manufacturing showed that the actual values of the outer dimensions and wall thickness were on average (99.7 ± 0.5) % and (90.6 ± 3.2) % of the nominal CAD model, respectively. Measured wall thickness was used to adjust the CAD models for FEM analysis. The evaluated data are summarized in Appendix B.

3.1.1 Stainless steel 316L

Comparison of the results (Figure 5a) showed an increase in *SEA* with the position of the reinforcement closer to the centre of the cell (except V00). The increase in absorbed energy was also correlated with a higher value of $R_{\sigma_{plateau}}$. However, the $R_{\sigma_{plateau}}$ value was mostly lower for reinforced unit cells than for No Reinf. configuration, so the reinforcements showed a great potential for enhancing the energy absorption performance.

The deformation of the reinforcements was caused by the inward deflection of the arms. The exception was the V00 configuration, where the position of the reinforcements directly in the middle of the cell led to their merge, thus over-reinforcing the region and causing a global buckling. For this reason, no deformation of the reinforcements occurred, which made the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ dependence completely different compared to the remaining configurations (Figure 5b).

There are two characteristic regions within the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curve, approximately copying the plateau characteristic, which were separated by the moment of contact of the deformed reinforcements with the horizontal arms. This contact occurred for all configurations, but it occurred later for the reinforcement closer to the centre, thus the deformed reinforcements were oriented more in the vertical direction (loading direction). This led to a higher increase in the eng. stress and hence the *SEA* value. On the other hand, as the distance of the reinforcement from the centre increased, lower eng. stress peak was observed, which had a negative impact on the total amount of absorbed energy. In fact, reinforcements in configurations V15, V20 and V25 were subjected to minimal deformation

(due to the proximity of the horizontal arms) and the cell compression was allowed primarily through deformation of the arms in the central region (**Figure 6a**).

It is also evident that the peak eng. stress within the first plateau region was up to three times higher for reinforced unit cells. The reinforcements prevented the arms from deflecting inward, thereby increased the force required to compress the unit cell. The closer the reinforcements were to the centre of the cell, the more resistance it put against the arm deflection due to the larger lever arm.

Considering the implemented reinforcements, it was expected, that the onset of densification would occur earlier as described by Gibson et al. [4] and Li et al. [34]. But according to the densification efficiency (η_D), which considers the relative density (i.e. the presence of reinforcements), the densification occurred too early compared to the specimen without reinforcements ($\eta_{D V\#\#} \approx 0.57$; $\eta_{D No Reinf.} = 0.78$). A slightly asymmetric deformation of samples resulted in layering the deformed walls that created a kind of frame structure, leading to an earlier densification (**Figure 6b**). This pattern of deformation is a result of increased sensitivity of the structure to imperfections in the geometry/loading conditions due to the presence of reinforcements. This behaviour should be considered if shear loading conditions are likely to occur.

Figure 5. a) Summary of the output parameters for both experimental and FEM testing; b) Eng. stress-strain curves with highlighted moments of reinforcements collision and densification; experimental data (red line) is compared with FEM (black dashed line) and with cell without reinforcement (gray line, config. No Reinf.).

Deformation maps in **Figure 6a** highlight the plasticizing regions where the energy was primarily dissipated. The first case for $\epsilon = 0.14$ (1.56 mm compression) captures the initiation zones where plastic hinges were formed. These locations became the main points around which the rotation of the "rigid" walls took place. No significant areas of plasticized material were formed at the connections of the reinforcements and the arms. Compared to the No Reinf., new plastic hinges were formed only in the inflection point of reinforcements (**Figure 6c**), at least in configurations with reinforcements closer to the centre (V05, V10, V15). It was assumed that new hinges will form at the connections of the reinforcements and the arms, too. However, these connections behaved more like a rigid joint, rather than a rotational one represented by the formation of a plastic hinge. These

findings can guide the further design of novel metamaterial by implementing more inflection points of the reinforcements to increase the number of plastic hinges dissipating energy.

The second case for $\epsilon = 0.42$ (4.69 mm compression) shows the state of the sample slightly before the complete compression. Engagement of the primarily formed plastic hinges on energy dissipation is clearly captured on the strain maps. For samples V05 and V10, the plasticized regions are approximately evenly distributed across the entire sample, i.e. including the reinforcements. For the remaining configurations, the reinforcements contributed less to energy dissipation. Since the reinforcements were further from the cell's centre, this led to the creation of a low-stiffness area at the centre of the cell. Therefore, only the deformation of this part was responsible for most of the total compression, which was reflected in the amount of deformed material and dissipated energy (SEA value).

The FEM simulations results had very good agreement with experimental ones. The largest difference was obtained for the V00 configuration, where the global buckling was captured in a different mode. This shows a significant sensitivity of the configuration to minor geometry/loading imperfection (e.g. exact wall thickness).

Figure 6. a) Strain map for eq. total strain for: $\epsilon = 0.14$; main locations of initialization of plastic hinges; and $\epsilon = 0.42$; main locations contributing to energy dissipation; b) effect of a/symmetric deformation on wall layering and densification value; c) assumed and observed formation of plastic hinges.

3.1.2 NiTi alloy

Similar results as with the stainless steel were assumed also with NiTi alloy, but the experimental testing of single unit cells showed an unexpected material behaviour. Fabricated samples from NiTi alloy showed insufficient results in terms of low ductility of the material during

compression tests. As can be seen in **Figure 7** the single unit cells were able to reach an eng. strain of only about 10 %. The material was not able to undergo large plastic deformation and so it broke in the early stage of deformation.

Maximum stress and strain values within the bulk material were located, as expected, at the hinge positions – these can be clearly visible in the **Figure 7** as locations of material rupture. According to DIC records and FEM simulations, the values of stress and strain at this moment were approximately 1250 MPa and 0,18 mm/mm, respectively. When compared to material model definition [42], this is beyond the super-elastic behaviour of NiTi alloy and all the material should be in the Martensite phase, but is still below the load capacity of the material. Possible cause of this poor mechanical properties can be a thin-walled geometry of the structure and/or insufficient process parameters for manufacturing such geometry. Because of the thin-walled geometry, the mechanical properties could be different from those of bulk material. Thin walls usually have greater surface roughness and the cooling rate is much faster, resulting in poor mechanical properties, increased stress concentration and lower ductility [44–46]. It can be also difficult to produce defect-free NiTi alloy as it is susceptible to cracking during manufacturing due to high residual stresses, nickel evaporation or incompletely melted powder [47].

Within the configurations tested, two unique events could be recognized, labelled as *crack* and *break* in **Figure 7**. *Crack* label corresponds with the formations of cracks of the hinges, however, further compression led to similar or even higher eng. stress. On the other hand, *break* label corresponds with complete destruction of the sample or no further increase in eng. stress. *Break* event was observed for all configurations, but *crack* occurred only for V15, V20 and V25 configuration, i.e. configurations with reinforcements further from the cell centre. Such placement of the reinforcements resulted in a smaller gap between them and the horizontal arms, and thus earlier collision during deformation. This contact led to a stiffening of the geometry, which prevented the material from exceeding its load capacity in a sufficient volume to cause immediate destruction of the specimen. For the remaining configurations, i.e. No Reinf., V00, V05 and V10, the maximum stress and strain values in the formed hinges was far beyond the material limit, even before the contact of the reinforcements and the horizontal arms. Therefore, no *crack* and only *break* event was present.

Figure 7. NiTi: Eng. stress–strain curves with highlighted moments of first cracks (*crack*) and complete destruction (*break*); experimental data (blue line) is compared with FEM (black/grey dashed line) and with cell without reinforcement (gray line, config. No Reinf.).

Eng. stress–strain curves obtained from FEM analysis followed the same trend in response progress as experimental ones for both materials. **Figure 8a** compares the eng. stress–strain curves. Configurations No Reinf. and V15 were chosen for demonstration purpose as all other configurations share the same trend. Samples from NiTi alloy showed almost the same response as that from stainless steel, differing only in the absolute value of eng. stress, which was higher. Due to this, NiTi alloy samples were able to absorb more energy, thus reaching higher values of SEA (approx. two times higher). Deviation from plateau characteristic ($R_{\sigma,plateau}$) and densification efficiency (η_D) values were approx. 20 % and 5 % lower for stainless steel, respectively. Configurations No Reinf. and V00 were the only exception due to a different mode of global buckling captured in the simulations.

Figure 8. Comparison of stainless steel and NiTi unit cell for FEM results: a) demonstration of the same trend in eng. stress–strain curves progress; b) main output parameters.

3.1.3 Reinforced unit cell assesment

The distance of the reinforcements from the cell centre was crucial in terms of stable deformation and amount of absorbed energy. Configurations with reinforcements in the centre of the cell should be avoided, because of unstable deformation due to global buckling. The risk of global buckling would be even higher as the number of cells increases. For investigated configurations in this study, the range from $V \approx 0.5$ to 1.5 mm should be the most sufficient, because they were able to combine high value of SEA , low deviation from plateau characteristic and stable deformation.

Obtained findings on the use of reinforcements point to their benefits and, moreover, not only in the field of energy absorbers. In particular, the secondary step increase of the load capacity after contact of reinforcements and horizontal arms can be beneficial for ensuring the safety even after the first load capacity has been exceeded.

The results can be used as a guide to define the appropriate area for the reinforcement's connection, but the specific values of the location should be considered individually in the context of the structure type, the number of cells used, the t_A/t_R ratio, etc.

From obtained results, NiTi alloy would be a better choice for structures for energy absorption, as it achieved higher values of SEA , while having $R_{\sigma_plateau}$ and η_D similar to 316L. However, the unsuitable behaviour of additively manufactured NiTi alloy is a serious obstacle that does not allow a reliable use in real life applications. Therefore, a deeper insight into mechanical properties of additively manufactured NiTi alloy is needed to better understand the influence of wall thickness on the material behaviour. Until that, the full potential of NiTi alloy for energy absorbers cannot be exploited and stainless steel will be more suitable for manufacturing a reliable high-performance structure for energy absorption.

3.2. High-performance structure

3.2.1 Single parameter analysis

Based on the criterium in **Section 2.5** the 5×5 unit cell structure was chosen (**Figure 9a**). Structures with $R_A = R_V = 1.5$ mm achieved higher SEA values and lower deviation from the plateau characteristic compared to other configurations. Lower value of R_A significantly increased the risk of unstable deformation pattern because the arms were oriented close to the loading direction. On the other hand, higher values led to sooner contact of opposite arms resulting in early densification and lower SEA . $V = 1$ mm was chosen for the final geometry, as it was able to absorb more energy at a sufficiently low value of $R_{\sigma_plateau} < 10\%$ compared to other configurations. The effect of reinforcement location was discussed in detail in **Section 3.1.1**. In terms of stability of the deformation, structures with $t_R = 0.75$ mm and *combined* was closest to the plateau characteristic ($R_{\sigma_plateau} < 10\%$). For uniform thickness $t_R = 0.75$ mm, only horizontal reinforcements were deforming (**Figure 9b**), while with $t_R = \textit{combined}$ all reinforcements in one layer deformed simultaneously.

Figure 9. Overview from designing the high-performance structures: a) number of cell independence; b) parametrization of t_R .

Configurations with the smallest deviation from the plateau characteristic, good absorption performance and the minimum risk of global buckling were selected. **Table 4** summarizes chosen parameters of designed structures and a reference structure without reinforcements. These configurations were manufactured from stainless steel 316L and then tested.

Table 4. Overview of designed high-performance structures with 5×5 cells ($R_A = 1.5$ mm; $t_A = 1.0$ mm)

Configuration	S0	S1	S2
V (mm)	-	1.0	1.0
t_R (mm)	-	0.75	0.5 + 0.75

3.2.2 FEM analysis and Experimental validation

Obtained results confirmed the benefits of reinforcements in the DRHC structure as can be seen in **Figure 10a**.

The S1 configuration, with uniform thickness of all reinforcements, achieved homogenous stiffness in all sections leading to smooth deformation and the best performance (**Figure 10b**). Compared to the S0 reference geometry, the *SEA* value achieved was more than 70% higher, while achieving a significantly smaller deviation from the plateau characteristic. The uniform deformation of S1 also compensated its earlier densification.

Figure 10. a) Summary of the key output parameters for both experimental and FEM testing; b) Eng. stress-strain curves; c) deformation process comparison for experiment and FEM simulations.

The eng. stress-strain curves of tested configurations are shown in **Figure 10b**. The fluctuation in the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ was caused due the layer-by-layer deformation. For S0, these fluctuations were partially

damped by global buckling of the structure. A detailed analysis of $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ curve for the best-performing structure S1 is shown in **Figure 11**. Video records of compression test for all configurations can be found in **Supplementary section**. The description of the **Figure 11** is given below:

0. Original state before loading.
1. Alignment of the upper and bottom outer arms leading to settlement of the upper plate on the main body of the structure.
2. Overcoming the load capacity of the structure followed by layer-by-layer deformation with a slight decrease in the eng. stress. The first layer involved was the very bottom row in which the horizontal reinforcements deformed, allowing deflection of the arms.
3. Deformation of the horizontal reinforcements in the bottom row to its extreme position (contact with the arms) leading to an increase in the stiffness of these cells. This led to an increase in σ and deformation of a new row.
4. Repetition of steps 2 and 3 for other layers.
5. In all rows, the horizontal reinforcements had already deformed to their extreme position. The load capacity of the structure was now dependent on the stiffness of the vertical reinforcements.
6. After a slight increase in the eng. stress, the vertical reinforcements also started to deform. This time it was simultaneously for the three middle rows, which is reflected in the smooth progression of the eng. stress up to the point of densification.
7. Full compression of the middle rows. Steep increase in σ and onset of the densification ε_D .
8. Full compression of all layers. An even steeper increase in the eng. stress resulting from the contact of all arms and reinforcements. Further displacement of the compression plate thus led to a compression of the base material rather than the structure geometry itself.
9. Test termination.

Figure 11. Detailed analysis of eng. stress-strain curve (experimental) of S1 structure

The compression process was similar for S2, but the deformation of the actual layer did not end at the moment of contact of the reinforcements with the arms (step 3 in **Figure 11**). But, due to the designed different thickness of the horizontal and vertical reinforcements, the complete compression of the row was achieved (**Figure 10c**). This resulted in greater fluctuation in eng. stress and thus lower absorption performance. Therefore, a similar thickness of reinforcements and arms ($t_R \approx t_A$) is better for effective energy dissipation.

It was found that only the middle three layers were completely compressed at the evaluated moment of densification for all configurations. Therefore, the value of densification was relatively low ($\varepsilon_D \approx 0.4$; $\eta_D \approx 0.5$). The outer two layers, which were in direct contact with the compression plates, were not allowed to deform in the same way as the inner rows. Thus, it can be expected that as the number of cells in the loading direction increases, the influence of the outer rows would become less significant and densification could be achieved at eng. strain values greater than 50 %.

By comparing experiment and FEM simulations, a very good agreement was found in the deformation process and eng. stress-strain curve. All evaluated data from this section are summarized in Appendix C.

3.2.3 High-performance structures assesment

Implementation of reinforcements was beneficial for structures, but they were very sensitive to the parameters R_A , V and t_R , resulting in high chance of global buckling. Approximately the same stiffness of all regions of configuration S1 caused evenly distributed load across the whole structure resulting in the best performance. However, it should be possible to reach even better performance, if the densification occurs later. This could be achieved with higher number of cells in the direction of applied force, when the outermost row of structure would have negligible impact on the deformed pattern.

There is still some flexibility for further adjustment of the mechanical properties of the structures by changing the thickness of the arms t_A . The new t_A values should be close to the tested value of 1 mm, i.e. in the interval of approximately 0.8 to 1.2 mm (t_R in scale). This is because a smaller t_A could change the deformation mechanism to a twisting collapse of the arms instead of their rotation around plastic hinges. In the case of a larger thickness, the arms could behave as a bulk material and could no longer deflect inwards, thus the reinforcement would not be used efficiently [38].

4. Conclusions

This study focused on an investigation and systematic design of additively manufactured auxetic structure using FEM analysis and experimental verification in the form of a quasi-static compression test. The main achievement of the work is the explanation of consequences of implementing the reinforcements on the energy absorption performance. Using obtained results, a high-performance auxetic structure was designed that achieved enhanced properties compared to a reference structure. The main findings of this study are as follows:

- The addition of reinforcements to the RHC cell resulted in up to three times higher load capacity and *SEA* value. For the configurations tested, the deformation of the reinforcements was due to inward deflection of the arms, which indicated a suitable position of the reinforcements near the centre of the cell, in the range of $V \approx 0.5$ to 1.5 mm. Reinforcements placed elsewhere significantly disrupted the homogeneity of the material distribution, creating regions of higher and lower stiffness that resulted in unstable deformation. Based on the obtained distribution of the plasticised material, the assumption of plastic hinge formation at the connection points of the reinforcement to the arms was disproved.
- The DRHC structure type showed a more suitable deformation pattern for the use of reinforcements than the RHC type. In addition, the DRHC type is symmetrical along two planes, thus providing the same load response for two different – mutually perpendicular – directions. The DRHC structure of 5×5 cell size with reinforcements and nominal parameters $R_A = 1.5$ mm; $V = 1$ mm $t_A = 1$ mm and $t_R = 0.75$ mm achieved more than 70% higher *SEA* and stable deformation close to the plateau characteristic compared to the reference structure without reinforcements.

Presented findings can be used for designing new structures and modifying existing ones in a more targeted manner to achieve efficient energy dissipation and high absorption performance. Further research of the observed issue could investigate exact definition of the parameters interval to achieve optimal performance, the combination of methods mentioned in the literature leading to an increase in absorbed energy, or the behaviour of specimens with reinforcements under general loading conditions.

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization, V.S.; methodology, V.S., O.Č., J.J. and J.H.; software, V.S., J.H. and O.Č.; validation, O.Č. and M.T.; formal analysis, V.S.; investigation, V.S.; resources, D.K.; data curation, O.Č. and V.S.; writing—original draft preparation, V.S.; writing—review and editing, O.Č., J.J., D.K., M.T.; visualization, V.S.; supervision, O.Č., M.T. and D.K.; project administration, M.T. and D.K.; funding acquisition, D.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Abbreviations

2D	Two-dimensional	$R_{\sigma_{plateau}}$	deviation from plateau characteristic
BCC	Body Centered Cubic	SEA	Specific Energy Absorption
BCC-6H	Body Centered Cubic – 6 Hollows	S_{str}	area of specimen projection in the direction of the force
BCCz	Body Centered Cubic with struts in z-direction	t_A	arm thickness
CAD	Computer Aided Design	t_R	reinforcement thickness
CoF	Coefficient of Friction	V	position of reinforcement
DIC	Digital Image Correlation	V_{str}	volume of envelope cuboid of the specimen
DRHC	Double Re-entrant Honeycomb	x_0, y_0	initial dimensions in the direction of coordinate axis
EXP	Experiment	X	displacement in x -direction
FEM	Finite Element Method	Y	displacement in y -direction
RHC	Re-entrant Honeycomb	y	actual displacement
SLM	Selective Laser Melting	ε	engineering strain
TPMS	Triply Periodic Minimal Surface	ε_D	densification
A	elongation at break	η	energy absorption efficiency
E_S	elastic modulus of bulk material	η_D	efficiency of densification
E_t	tangent modulus	μ	Poisson's number
F	(Reaction) force	ρ_{REL}	measured relative density
H_0	initial height of specimen	ρ_S	density of bulk material
m^*	measured mass of specimen	σ	engineering stress
R_m	ultimate tensile strength	σ_{max}	peak engineering stress
$R_{p0,2}$	yield strength (0.2% proof stress)		
R_A	deflection of arm		
R_R	deflection of reinforcement		

Appendix A

Output parameters

Main output parameters calculated from eng. stress-strain curve are listed below.

Onset of densification (ε_D) was set at the point of the highest **energy absorption efficiency (η)** value according to (1) and (2) [27], where σ and ε are eng. stress and eng. strain, respectively.

$$\varepsilon_D = \varepsilon(\eta_{max}) \quad (1)$$

$$\eta(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{\sigma(\varepsilon)} \int_0^\varepsilon \sigma(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon \quad (-) \quad (2)$$

Densification efficiency (η_D) was used to assess the reached moment of densification. It was calculated using formula (3) [1]. **Relative density (ρ_{REL})** is given by (4), where m^* is measured mass, ρ_S is material density and V_{str} is volume of envelope cuboid.

$$\eta_D = \frac{\varepsilon_D}{1 - \rho_{REL}} \quad (-). \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{REL} = \frac{m^*}{\rho_S V_{str}} \quad (-) \quad (4)$$

Specific energy absorption (SEA) was determined according to formula (5) [37] from the $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ curve and measured relative density.

$$SEA = \frac{\int_0^{\varepsilon_D} \sigma(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon}{\rho_S \rho_{REL}} \quad (\text{J kg}^{-1}). \quad (5)$$

Deviation from plateau characteristic ($R_{\sigma_plateau}$) was used to quantify the amount of potentially absorbed energy with ideal plateau characteristic compared to really absorbed one. The formula (6) is for evaluating $R_{\sigma_plateau}$, where σ_{max} is maximum eng. stress before densification ε_D :

$$R_{\sigma_plateau} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{max} \varepsilon_D}{\int_0^{\varepsilon_D} \sigma(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon} - 1 \right) \cdot 100 \quad (\%). \quad (6)$$

Data from the **DIC camera recordings** were used for single cell with reinforcements to create strain maps, in the form of *Eng. Equivalent Strain (von Mises)*. Furthermore, recordings were used to see the deformation process to pick up critical moments without any measurable variable.

Appendix B

Table B1. Output parameters from experimental test for unit cells from stainless steel 316L.

Configuration	ρ_{REL} (-)	SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ε_D (-)
316L - EXP	V00	0.372	9.22	28.27	0.63	89.27
	V05	0.382	16.93	41.72	0.71	165.95
	V10	0.386	14.84	58.74	0.72	163.48
	V15	0.383	8.00	32.69	0.53	98.70
	V20	0.392	6.51	27.89	0.54	79.58
	V25	0.398	5.31	29.66	0.52	70.14
No Reinf.	0.279	5.45	55.29	0.76	34.14	0.550

Table B2. Output parameters from experimental test for unit cells from NiTi alloy (all parameters are evaluated up to break of the sample, approx. 10 % of eng. strain).

Configuration	ρ_{REL} (-)	SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ε_D (-)
NiTi - EXP	V00	0.431	2.79	72.45	0.16	143.00
	V05	0.440	1.83	53.23	0.13	104.41
	V10	0.444	1.03	56.50	0.10	82.74
	V15	0.447	1.74	38.87	0.17	73.12
	V20	0.451	2.01	44.87	0.19	81.15
	V25	0.454	1.85	47.59	0.16	87.34
No Reinf.	0.325	0.46	53.33	0.06	38.32	0.56

Table B3. Output parameters from FEM analysis for unit cells from stainless steel 316L.

Configuration		SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ϵ_D (-)
316L - FEM	V00	13.83	6.83	0.76	102.60	0.457
	V05	16.63	37.84	0.77	162.03	0.457
	V10	13.96	43.60	0.74	149.09	0.438
	V15	7.66	22.05	0.55	94.99	0.323
	V20	7.21	21.06	0.59	84.18	0.344
	V25	5.11	14.37	0.53	63.92	0.306
	No Reinf.	5.09	34.40	0.85	28.25	0.589

Table B4. Output parameters from FEM analysis for unit cells from NiTi alloy (all parameters are evaluated up to full compression).

Configuration		SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ϵ_D (-)
NiTi - FEM	V00	21.92	43.60	0.79	187.84	0.455
	V05	31.26	35.81	0.81	259.18	0.455
	V10	20.95	38.27	0.68	212.87	0.381
	V15	14.50	29.81	0.60	159.23	0.334
	V20	15.73	32.95	0.68	159.00	0.374
	V25	10.36	18.08	0.55	116.91	0.300
	No Reinf.	11.44	10.09	0.87	43.56	0.592

Appendix C

Table C1. Output parameters from experimental test for structures from stainless steel 316L.

Configuration		ρ_{REL} (-)	SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ϵ_D (-)
316L	S0	0.188	3.37	47.07	0.58	15.69	0.471
-	S1	0.261	5.47	17.67	0.49	37.20	0.401
EXP	S2	0.248	3.84	46.734	0.46	32.41	0.343

Table C2. Output parameters from FEM analysis for structures from stainless steel 316L.

Configuration		SEA (J/g)	$R_{\sigma_plateau}$ (%)	η_D (-)	σ_{max} (MPa)	ϵ_D (-)
316L	S0	3.36	37.68	0.62	14.38	0.498
-	S1	5.13	26.13	0.57	34.60	0.413
FEM	S2	4.10	39.73	0.53	31.36	0.386

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